

MATERIALS AND PROCESS SELECTION FOR COST-PERFORMANCE EFFECTIVE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Composite materials offer the designer a very wide range of choice of reinforcing fibre, reinforcement format, matrix and manufacturing route. A successful design must meet the technical specification and production requirements at an acceptable cost. The production rate, total production run and availability of processing facilities will further influence both choice of materials and manufacturing route. A methodology is proposed for cost and performance prediction so that the alternatives may be evaluated on the basis of an objective assessment of cost and performance. The concept of a cost-performance index is introduced. This requires that a value be established for critical parameters of performance, e.g. stiffness and mass. This is illustrated with reference to a simple notional component.

KEYWORDS: cost, mechanical performance, continuous fibre laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials must compete with traditional materials and with each other in the engineering market place. The generally perceived advantages of composites lie in their greater structural efficiency, their ability to be tailored for specific applications, their possibilities for parts consolidation and a number of secondary advantages such as reduced corrosion. These advantages must be offset against the generally higher costs of the raw materials and the need to use unfamiliar manufacturing processes. In order to be able to compare the relative performance and economic aspects of different materials choices for a given application it is necessary that both performance and cost must be effectively analysed and predicted. It is also desirable that an equivalence between performance and cost should be established. It must be possible to answer the question: What is the value of an increase in performance? If we confine ourselves to a consideration of structural efficiency. Performance might be defined in terms of the mass of a component or structure to meet a given service loading scenario. We may then establish a monetary value for mass saving expressed in terms of \$/kg. This may then be used as a yardstick for comparison of alternative materials and manufacturing choices.

Structural Efficiency

This may be measured simply in terms of the mass of the part or structure which just meets the requirements of the mechanical specification. The critical performance parameter may be stiffness, or some aspect of strength, e.g. tension, compression, shear, creep, fatigue or

fracture toughness. In general all of these parameters may be assigned a numerical value. Furthermore the well developed methodologies of micro-mechanics, laminate plate analysis and finite element modelling techniques enable a good estimate of performance to be attained if the key elements of the constitution and structure of the composite are known. These are generally the properties of the fibre and those of the matrix, the fibre fraction, V_f , and the overall reinforcement architecture. In the present work flexural stiffness is used to illustrate typical aspects of performance.

Estimating Cost

This is rather more difficult and inexact due to the complexity of the problem and the lack of accurate data. Every effort has been made to obtain meaningful data but it is accepted that the values used may not all be realistic. Never-the-less they serve to illustrate the principles necessary to make objective cost-performance comparisons. The key aspects of the cost analysis are:

- Raw materials
- Conversion
- Tooling
- Labour
- Plant
- Consumables
- Materials utilisation

Raw materials: This is the cost of the basic fibre and resin in the case of conventional fibre reinforced polymer composites. Fibre costs vary quite considerably from the order of \$1/kg for the most basic forms of E-glass to in excess of \$1000/kg for the more exotic boron and SiC mono-filaments. Resin costs are less variable but there are still significant differences between a commodity resin such as an unsaturated polyester or polypropylene at a few \$/kg and the high temperature thermosets, such as polyimide or thermoplastics such as poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) which may cost more than \$50/kg.

Conversion includes processes like weaving, braiding and pre-pregging in which the reinforcement is converted from the basic continuous roving, which is the usual format for primary supply, into a sheet, web or bulk format, possibly incorporating the resin, which is a more suitable feedstock for certain downstream processing operations. The cost of the conversion process may be offset by a more convenient and cheaper overall process. In some processes, such as filament winding or pultrusion, the fibre roving may be converted into the final product in a single processing operation. Such processes have the advantage of using the raw materials in their most basic, and least costly format. In other cases the fibre may be woven into a cloth, then impregnated with resin, cut into shapes and then laminated onto a tool. The cost of the intermediate conversion and handling operations may be substantial but the overall process may still be viable due to better performance or greater productivity.

Tooling costs may also be significant. A critical consideration is the required rate of production and the total number of parts to be manufactured. Simple disposable tooling may be used for "one off" applications, especially for very large mouldings. The whole cost of the tool then contributes to the cost of each part. More durable, but still cheap, tools may allow the manufacture of up to 100 parts from a single tool set. This allows the mould cost to be amortised over the greater number of parts. Very complex metal tools used with the more

highly automated processes, such as injection moulding, may be good for the production of tens of thousands of parts at very high rates. In general processes using simple tooling tend to be slow and labour intensive whilst the reverse is true for the highly automated processes. Another aspect of the choice of tooling and process is that achievable levels of performance may be a function of the process. Hand laid laminates using uniaxial prepreg may be the most structurally efficient and are also more flexible in that the lay-up, and hence structural performance, may be easily modified. In contrast, a reinforced thermoplastic injection moulding compound has very limited fibre content and there is much less control of the overall fibre orientation. Thus, performance and cost are lower but productivity is much higher. In the examples considered below the actual tooling costs are generally quite a small proportion of the final cost of the part, but labour costs can be a major factor.

Another important contribution to cost is the capital cost of the required plant and its operating costs. This is probably the most difficult aspect on which to obtain meaningful data. It is easy to establish that an autoclave, say, may cost several million dollars to purchase and commission. However, the way in which this capital expenditure is allocated to the cost of the parts subsequently manufactured is shrouded in uncertainty due to varying accountancy practices and local taxation laws. The principle used in the present work is to assume a plant life of 10 years and that it is operated continuously for the manufacture of parts similar to the standard moulding discussed.

The remaining factors are consumables and materials utilisation. In some processes, particularly autoclave moulding of prepreg, quite large amounts of relatively expensive consumables are used. These include bleeder and breather materials and bagging film. They can seldom be used more than once and therefore contribute directly to the cost of the product. Materials utilisation, often termed the “fly to buy ratio” in the aerospace industry, is simply the fraction of the bought-in materials which finishes up in the product. Again for prepreg there is considerable wastage so that the utilisation factor may be as low as 0.5. For a fibre reinforced thermoplastic injection moulding, where sprue and scrap may often be directly recycled, the value approaches 1.0.

ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

The basis of the present analysis is to use a simple generic component for comparison of mechanical performance when using different materials and cost using different materials and manufacturing routes. The component is a 1 m² stiffened panel with a gentle single curvature. It is supported across the two curved edges and uniformly loaded in bending. This shape is typical of composite components used in many different applications: e.g. A hood for a car, a fuselage panel on an aircraft, part of the hull for a yacht or a storage tank for containing liquid or particulate materials. The performance requirements and economic constraints would, however, be very different for these applications and would lead to different choices of composite system and manufacturing process.

This component lends itself to manufacture by a wide variety of processes ranging from autoclave consolidation of prepreg, through resin film infusion [RFI] and resin transfer moulding [RTM] variants, to injection moulding from a moulding compound. The range of processes and materials considered together with the identification codes used are set out in Table 1. The laminates are based on E-glass, a typical high-strength carbon [HC] and an

intermediate-modulus carbon fibre [IM]. All laminates are in a quasi-isotropic configuration. For each material and process combination the panel thickness and stiffener dimensions

Table 1: Materials and processes considered

LAMINAT E CODE	FIBRE	FORMAT	PROCESS	V_f	IN-PLANE STIFFNESS E_1 [GPa]
GF-RM-IM	E-glass	BMC	Injection mould	0.25	6.5
GF-RM-CM	E-glass	SMC	Press mould	0.30	7.5
GF-RM-RT	E-glass	Random mat	RTM	0.30	9.9
GF-WR-RT	E-glass	Woven cloth		0.45	14.9
HC-WR-RT	HS carbon	Woven cloth		0.45	37.1
GF-NC-RT	E-glass	Non-crimp fabric	RTM	0.50	18.3
HC-NC-RT	HS carbon				45.6
GF-NC-PM	E-glass	Non-crimp fabric	RFI	0.55	19.8
HC-NC-PM	HS carbon		Press mould		49.5
IM-NC-PM	IM carbon				61.2
GF-NC-AC	E-glass	Non-crimp fabric	RFI	0.55	19.8
HC-NC-AC	HS carbon		Autoclave		49.5
IM-NC-AC	IM carbon				61.2
GF-PP-AC	E-glass	UD Prepreg	Autoclave	0.60	22.0
AR-PP-AC	Aramid				30.0
HC-PP-AC	HS carbon				55.0
IM-PP-AC	IM carbon				68.0

have been adjusted so that all panels have similar initial flexural stiffness in bending. The mass of each variant is then estimated and is used as the basis for assessing structural efficiency. The cost of materials and manufacture has also been estimated. This, of course, would vary according to the scale of production. The basis used here is to set the annual productivity on the number of components which could be produced from a single set of tools in a factory working a single shift system for 250 days/year. The only variation is for the two most automated processes considered, the press-moulded sheet moulding compound [SMC] and the injection-moulded bulk moulding compound [BMC] which are notionally operated on a 3-shift, 24 hours/day basis also for 250 days/year. Inevitably the materials purchase costs and the estimates of process costs must be approximate, but they are based on previous work [1-6], actual quotations and the best available information obtainable from toolmakers and suppliers. It should be mentioned that many commercial organisations are reluctant to release any detailed cost data.

RESULTS

The basic results are summarised in Table 2. This shows the thickness and mass of the different options and the cost, with a breakdown showing contributions of materials, tooling, plant amortisation and operation and labour as percentages of the total.

Table 2: Performance and cost analysis

CODE	THICK-NESS [mm]	MASS [kg]	PARTS p.a.	UNIT COST [\$]	COST BREAKDOWN [%]			
					Matls	Tooling	Plant	Labour
GF-RM-IM	5.50	11.07	45x10 ³	128	90	1	3	6
GF-RM-CM	5.00	10.36	12x10 ³	182	79	2	2	17
GF-RM-RT	4.25	8.66		459	13	15	4	68
GF-WR-RT	2.85	7.32	750	581	22	12	3	63
HC-WR-RT	1.68	2.92		723	39	9	3	49
GF-NC-RT	2.70	6.46	750	602	24	12	3	61
HC-NC-RT	1.45	2.55		683	37	10	3	50
GF-NC-PM	2.70	6.30		782	30	8	4	58
HC-NC-PM	1.35	2.40	500	823	37	6	5	52
IM-NC-PM	1.10	1.93		1162	56	4	3	37
GF-NC-AC	2.70	6.30		2161	11	6	36	47
HC-NC-AC	1.35	2.40	250	2321	18	6	34	42
IM-NC-AC	1.10	1.93		2712	30	5	29	36
GF-PP-AC	2.48	5.87		2582	19	5	31	45
AR-PP-AC	1.75	3.04	250	2823	27	4	28	41
HC-PP-AC	1.25	2.19		2391	15	6	33	46
IM-PP-AC	1.00	1.76		2583	22	5	31	42

It will be observed that there is almost an order of magnitude difference between the masses of the most and least structurally efficient system, whilst the costs range over three orders. The processes using autoclave consolidation are the most costly. There is no economic gain from using cheaper fibres for the prepreg-autoclave variant. This is because the laminates need a greater number of plies with consequent additional labour cost.

COST-PERFORMANCE INDEX

In order to facilitate an objective evaluation of the relative performance and cost, a *cost-performance index*, I_{pc} , is proposed. This requires that a value, v_p , be set for mass reduction. Values for v_p ranging from 1 to 10000 \$ per kg of mass saved have been used. The lower figure might be appropriate for automotive and general engineering and the higher values for spacecraft. The index is defined by:

$$I_{PC} = \frac{c_o + (m_o - m_i)v_p - c_i}{c_o} \quad (1)$$

where m_o and c_o are the mass and cost of a reference system, usually the cheapest of those being considered, and m_i and c_i the mass and cost of the system to be compared. The index will be zero for the reference system, a positive value of the index indicates a cost-performance advantage and a negative index a disadvantage. The quantity $(m_o - m_i)v_p$ is simply the added value due to mass saving. In the example the comparison has been made on the basis of stiffness and mass but any other performance criterion could be substituted for

stiffness. The results of this computation are given in Table 3 and illustrated graphically in Figs. 1-5 each for a different assumed value of ν_p .

Table 3: Cost-performance index

SYSTEM	COST-PERFORMANCE INDEX - I_{PC}				
	For indicated values of ν_p				
	1 \$/kg	10 \$/kg	100 \$/kg	1000 \$/kg	10000 \$/kg
GF-RM-IM	0	0	0	0	0
GF-RM-CM	-0.42	-0.37	0.13	5.13	55
GF-RM-RT	-2.57	-2.40	-0.70	16.24	186
GF-WR-RT	-3.51	-3.25	-0.61	25.76	289
HC-WR-RT	-4.58	-4.01	1.72	59.02	632
GF-NC-RT	-3.67	-3.34	-0.10	32.31	356
HC-NC-RT	-4.27	-3.67	2.32	62.23	661
GF-NC-PM	-5.07	-4.74	-1.38	32.16	368
HC-NC-PM	-5.36	-4.75	1.34	62.30	672
IM-NC-PM	-8.01	-7.36	-0.94	63.33	706
GF-NC-AC	-15.85	-15.51	-12.16	21.38	357
HC-NC-AC	-17.07	-16.46	-10.36	50.60	660
IM-NC-AC	-20.12	-19.47	-13.05	51.22	694
GF-PP-AC	-19.13	-18.77	-15.11	21.45	387
AR-PP-AC	-20.99	-20.43	-14.78	41.68	606
HC-PP-AC	-17.61	-16.99	-10.74	51.70	676
IM-PP-AC	-19.11	-18.45	-11.91	53.55	708

It will be noted in Table 3 that the index for the reference system is always zero. The value of the index for the comparison systems is dependent on the value chosen for ν_p and tends to be greater when a high value has been chosen. The best system is that with the highest positive index, the appropriate boxes are highlighted in Table 3. Thus for ν_p of 1 and 10 \$/kg the reference system, the injection moulded BMC is the most cost-performance effective. At 100 \$/kg the non-crimp high-strength carbon fabric processed by RTM is best, at 1000 \$/kg the RFI press-moulded IM carbon non-crimp fabric is favoured, whilst only at 10000 \$/kg does the most structurally efficient IM carbon prepreg become the system of choice, with the press-moulded RFI variant in close second place. This analysis has emphasised the economic disadvantages of autoclave based processing and the advantages of RTM and RFI in combination with non-crimp fabrics which offer the possibility of relatively high structural efficiency. It also shows that the choice of carbon in preference to E-glass may often be justified on cost-performance grounds. In real design situations the comparison will normally be over a much narrower range than that illustrated and more realistic materials and processing costs should be available. The methodology described should provide a useful tool at the preliminary stages of design.

Fig.:1 Cost-performance index for $v_p=1$ \$/kg

Fig. 2: Cost-performance index for $v_p=10$ \$/kg

Fig. 3: Cost-performance index for $v_p=100$ \$/kg

Fig. 4: Cost-performance index for $v_p=1000$ \$/kg

Fig. 5: Cost-performance index for $v_p=10000$ \$/kg

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